

NEGATIVE VALUE EXPRESSING BY PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

¹Z.Z.Isakova, ²G.Z.Shamsiddinova

¹PhD, Kokand pedagogical institute

²Student, Kokand pedagogical institute

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Abstract. In the modern linguistic over the worldwide language is considered one concept that it still has been researching field. Semantic structure category of value is one of the subject. This category of value is to be used to express some language units which consist of phrases, idioms, and words. In this unit lexical and grammatical meaning of word group can be stand with stability. A great number of linguists are studying on phraseological units such as words, colloques with various theories.

Keywords: phraseological units, metaphorical motivation, word combination, disappointment, notable characteristics, magical practice, positive, comparison.

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi zamon tilshunosligida jahon tillari haligacha tadqiq qilib kelayotgan sohalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Qiymatning semantik strukturasi kategoriyasi predmetlardan biridir. Ushbu qiymat turkumi iboralar, idiomalar va so'zlardan tashkil topgan ba'zi til birliklarini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi. Bu birlikda so'z turkumining leksik va grammatik ma'nosi barqaror turishi mumkin. Ko'pgina tilshunoslar so'z kabi frazeologik birliklar, turli xil nazariyalarga ega bo'lgan kollektivlar ustida o'rganmoqdalar.

Kalit so'zlar: frazeologik birliklar, metaforik motivatsiya, so'z birikmasi, umidsizlik, diqqatga sazovor xususiyatlar, sehrli amaliyot, ijobiy, taqqoslash.

Аннотация. В современной лингвистике во всем мире язык считается одной концепцией, область исследования которой до сих пор остается. Семантическая структура категории ценности является одной из предметных. Эту категорию значений следует использовать для выражения некоторых языковых единиц, состоящих из фраз, идиом и слов. В этом блоке лексическое и грамматическое значение группы слов может стоять устойчиво. Большое количество лингвистов изучают фразеологические единицы, такие как слова, коллекции, с различными теориями.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, метафорическая мотивация, словосочетание, разочарование, примечательные характеристики, магическая практика, позитив, сравнение.

Phraseological unity is kind of stable word combinations which this unity signify an expressive-evaluative degree of words. The meanings of phraseological unity is hold on different types of transformation which include metaphor, metonymy, comparison. In contrast to this, phraseological unity is different from semantic value of words that consist of homonymous, synonymous, antonymous combination of words. Phraseological word phrases are a sort of word combinations that the degree of semantic meaning of components is expressed value of words. This form of phraseological components assert quality of words. The great number of scientist, linguists studied on phraseological units who relate to V.V. Vinogradov, A.J.Smirnitsky, Sh.Rakhmatullaev.

Arnold classifies phraseological units according to the type of the component parts and the functioning of the whole. She states that "structured like phrases they function like words". [1] There are seven types of phraseological units in Arnold's structural classification: 1) nominal phrases, e.g., high life 2) verbal phrases, e.g., put one's head in a noose 3) adverbial phrases, e.g.,

by hook or by crook 4) adjectival phrases, e.g., as wet as a drowned rat 5) prepositional phrases, e.g., in accordance with 6) conjunctive phrases, e.g., as long as 7) interjectional phrases, e.g., well, I never did! [1]

A.J.Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units according to their stylistic features: 1) phraseological units (stylistically neutral, with faded metaphorical motivation, e.g., be in love, fall in love); 2) idioms (they are based on metaphor, they are emotionally and stylistically colored, e.g., cool as a cucumber). [2]

The 19th century Turkic scholar Mirza Kozimbek, based on the traditions of the time, used the word "phrase" in the meaning of "sentence" or "word" in his work, as in other figurative grammars written in Russian. When he says "phraseological compound", he is referring to larger linguistic units than words. Giving information about verbs in Turkic languages, he explained such linguistic units as "compound verbs" as "grief" and also "emergence" [5]. Phraseologies, phraseological unit, phraseology the general name of stable gardens, consisting of two or more words, spiritually equivalent to a related word combination or sentence, applied in a sense of integrity in a portable and indivisible

Professor Sh.Rakhmatullaev was the first to start the research of phraseology in Uzbek linguistics. Now in our linguistics phraseology is studied as a separate linguistic unit, the object of study of phraseology is defined in one way or another, their grammatical features are studied in one way or another, great monographs on stylistic possibilities have appeared, phraseological commentary dictionaries were created [6]

It can be considered that the issues of phraseological synonymy in Uzbek linguistics have been studied in detail. M.Vafoeva's "Phraseological synonyms in the Uzbek language and their structural semantic analysis" [3] can also be found in the review given in the dissertation. According to Vafoeva's dissertation, the first work on phraseology in Uzbek linguistics appeared in the early 50s of the XX century.

The phraseology "black as night" is a figurative expression "emphasizing the intense darkness". For example: *You might give me a hand at least Anne she said instead of standing with face as black as night.*

The phraseology "black in the face" is used to describe "sense of person who is frustrated in situation". For example: *And of course Archer will swear till he is black in the face that he did not do it.*

The phraseology "look black" is used to describe "facial features of person that appear serious." For sample: *My brother-in-law himself, who is all kindness in general, looked rather black upon me, when he found what I had been at.*

The phraseology "the black art" refers to "magical practice associate with negative force". For example: *Had I a thousand daughters by heaven I had as soon have them taught the black art as their alphabet.*

The phraseology "black as a crow" emphasize "the darkness of the subject." For example: *When at last they came down the long road into whorled the silent trees were black as ink.*

The phraseology "paint something in black" is used to describe "aesthetic preference of person." For example: *Percy had painted the situation in such lurid colors that Edward had made a dash and caught the midnight train, wearing his evening clothes, and without so much as a tooth-brush with him.*

A black-letter day [the day Poland was invaded was a black letter day for the world.]the black gang [they call us "the black gang" don't they shortly was indignant.]

The phraseology "black hand" is used to describe "the aim of negatives." For example: *Go back. Tell him before he leaves England he shall feel the hand of knish weighing, and it shall be heavier than the black hand.*

The black hole is used to "several notable characteristics of person." For sample: *Confinement to the black hole to be reserved for cases of Drunkenness, Riot, Violence or insolence to superiors.*

The phraseology "black as coals" is used to describe "something or someone that is dark color." For example: Marcel and lanky went ashore and saw strange dark men wearing white hoods and women going about completely veiled with eyes black as soles peering out seductively.

The black bottle "tell the landlord to get us supper" he said, we will crack a bottle to our luck.

The phraseology "black Maria" is used to "law enforcement that is transport of police or prisoner." For example: A minute later came the shriek of a siren, and round the corner came swinging the city's big patrol-wagon, the "Black Maria".

The phraseology "black hand" is used for "the aim of promoting go back." For example: *Tell him before he leaves England he shall feel the hand of knish weighing, and it shall be heavier than the black hand.*

The phraseology "blue fear and fear" describe "emotional state of people which is sadness." For example: *I hope you won't despise me for having been in a blue fear and fear.*

The phraseology "disappear into the blue" gives mean that "unexpected states of person." For example: *I saw him 2 years ago for the last time.*

The phraseology "till all is blue" describe "a temporal state of person." For example: *So I turned to him and slanged him till all was blue.*

The phraseology "be in the blues" means that "emotional state of person who is depressed". For example: *He is in the blues because of his illness.*

The phraseology "sing the blues" is used to describe "feelings of person that is discouraged". For example: *Roslyn was always, singing the blues because she was unhappy with her job.*

The phraseology "in a blue funk" means that "a state of fear." For example: *Philip came downstairs to find Mr. John despondent, in what he called a blue funk.*

The phraseology "a bit of the blue sky" describe situation that "easy progress." For example: After a long month of trouble and disappointment he financially saw a bit of blue sky.

The phraseology "see through blue glasses" give means that "regard actions in wrong way." For example: *Jenkins regards the position of affairs as very serious indeed.*

The phraseology "blue ruin" describe a character of person "who is beaver." For example: *Now Millie, you got yourself into that scrape, you know. I stood up for you because you were hard pressed, but I am not blind. You have got to promise me that you won't do it again: it is the first step to blue ruin.*

The phraseology "be not as green as one is cabbage-looking" [I am not the sort to be taken in by his gaff. I may look a fool but I am not as green as I am cabbage-looking]

The phraseology "do you see any green in my eye" describe personality that "mean a person was money hungry." For example: *But you cannot call the government imperialist he protested "see any green in my eye".*

The phraseology "green as a gooseberry" describe state of person "who is inexperienced in some field". For example: *His name was Green and he was as green as a gooseberry.*

The phraseology "get gray" describe to "become older during years". For example: *If John does not join the team, I won't get gray hair over it.*

The phraseology "grey –hound of the ocean" [They call the Mauretania ‘the grey-hound of the ocean.’ I wonder why, because it is too long and too thin and leaps up and down.]

The phraseology "in the pink" describe "a state of good health or positive." For example: Then he is ill, if ever I saw a gentleman in the pink.

The phraseology "a red dog" describe "game in the network." For example: Mr. Wiseman said "Let's play red dog for pennies few dollars left.

The phraseology "thin red line" give means that "limited potential forces." For example: *He is probably come to de-bag me and you "Bateman said to Peacock, British M.P dances till down while Nasser plots to blot out the thin red line.*

The phraseology "red as a beet" is used to "describe emotional statement of person who waste much more money". For example: *I rubbed him till he was red as a lobster all over by the time Il finished he was feeling better but l was exhausted.*

The phraseology "red as a fire" gives mean that "a state of person emotional statement of person who waste much more". For example: *l looked up from Jasper, my face red as a fire.*

The phraseology "red –handed" describe "negative thoughts." For example: *l did but tie one fellow who was taken red-handed in fact, to horns of a wild stag.*

The phraseology "get gray" For example: If John does not join the team, I won't get gray hair over it.

The phraseology "grey –hound of the ocean" For example: *They call the Mauretania "the grey-hound of the ocean." I wonder why, because it is too long and too thin and leaps up and down.*

The phraseology "black and tan" to describe "the coat color." For example: He took a pull at his pint of black and tan before answering.

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